

Paper 7

A CASE STUDY ANALYSIS ON INDIAN TRANSPORTATION INDUSTRY

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Abstract

The movement of goods from one point to another is complex in transportation industry and helps to contribute and increase GDP growth of the country. Transportation industry is a blend of the networks, infra-structure, equipment, information, technology and employee's to transport the large variety of products safely and efficiently throughout the nation and around the world although generally considered separate transportation entities, trains, plane, ship and trucks which actually part of an integrated network. In this case study we have analysed the employment opportunities, transportation industry forms and industry's effect on our life style. This study consists of three objectives that are gained by secondary data. Transportation industry has played major role on people's day to day life, business industry and growing economy. Road transportation is the best among the four modes of transportation as this gives larger connectivity and door to door service and its cheaper when compared to other mode of transportation. Rural sectors too get benefited by this mode of transportation. Agriculture and industrial sectors which are located far from city limits get connectivity of road transport.

Keywords: Employment, Growth, life style, Technology, Rural sector.

1. Introduction:

The Transportation industry is a vast eco system which covers everything related to major modes of transport, namely, Road, Rail, Marine, and Air transport. It has been appropriately remarked by Dr. Marshall, "Most effective economic fact of our times is not the development of manufacturing industries but that of the transport services." The relationship between economic growth and infrastructure investment is very evident. The faster the economy grows more the need for faster and reliable mode for transport for movement of goods and people. High growth of Indian economy is dynamic the demand for transportation industry. Transportation is the foundation stone of economic infrastructure. It aids in the development of trade, commerce and industry. Transportation removes the problem of place and facilitates the movement of goods from producers to consumers. It also helps in removing regional inequalities. Transportation industry contributed about 6.3% of GDP and it is majorly dominated by road sector. Additional 50% of freight and 90% of passenger traffic are handled by road. Government and private investments, rising exports, increasing regional movement of goods and passengers, growing FMCG sector and rising throwaway income are the foremost drivers of transportation industry in India. In order to enhance the connectivity across country, 100% FDI has been allowed in roads and Highway sector via automatic route.

The government of aviation sector has increased the FDI limit from 79% to 100% of which up to 49% is available under automatic route. The transportation industry is growing to its peak in overall development of our nation.

2. Objectives

- ❖ To know the employment opportunities from Transportation industries
- ❖ To analyse the Benefits of transport industry
- ❖ To know the challenges faced by this industry
- ❖

3. RESEARCH AND METHODOLOGY:

The proposed methodology is studies on the above said objectives are based on the secondary data. These projects consist of graphical representation obtained from secondary data. And for the selection the type of transport with associated weights of importance. And apart from this, expert in the area where consulted to arrive at a conclusion.

4. Discussions:

The transportation industry plays prominent role in the Indian economy. India’s transport network is one of the most extensive in the world. The share of the transport sector in overall infrastructure investments has increased from 2% of GDP during 1995-99 to an average of 2.6% of GDP between 2007 and 2011. Currently transport sector accounts for a share of 6.3% in Indian’s GDP. Road transportation has emerged as the dominant segment in India’s transportation sector with a share of 5.4% in India’s GDP. Transportation has assumed much significance in developing economy like India for rapid economic growth. If agriculture and industries are supposed to be the body of the country, transportation can be considered as nerves and veins of the economy. These days transportation is known as the symbol of civilization.

5. Mode Of transportation:

Modes of Transportation

Fig 1: Modes of Transportation

It means of physical movement of product and people are moving from one place to another place inside or outside of the country. There are several means of transportation. They are:

air, water, railways and road transportation. Other modes also exist, including pipelines, cable transport, and space transport. Following some the transport are explained below:

5.1 Rail Transport:

Rail transport is one of the most commonly used modes of long distance transportation in India. The first railway line lay down between Bombay and Thane in 1853. After that, the rail services have been developed a lot and today the largest rail network in Asia and the World's second largest network operated under a single management. It has 115,000 km of track length. It runs 12,617 trains to transmit over 23 million passengers daily. And at the time of independence, the total route length was 53,596km with 8209 engines, 19536 passenger bogies and 2,06,000 goods wagons. There are three types of rail lines in India: 1. Broad Gauge (1676mm) 2. Meter Gauge (1000mm) 3. Narrow Gauge (762mm). In 2015, India Railway contains of (108,706 km) route comprising Broad gauge (88,547), meter gauge (16,489km), and Narrow Gauge (3450 km). Railway have extended the size of market and thus stimulated the process of specialization. The bulk good can easily be transported by Railways from one place to another place. Railway has installed new source and new areas of production. They have helped in reaching the inaccessible areas if they do not provided knowledge of those areas. The Railway have been increased the mobility of labour and capital in which its turns to rapid industrialisation of the country. Still there are numberless problems in the in the path of steady growth. The main problems are stated as under: (1) the tracks are old and out dated: These old tracks cause many serious railway accidents. (2) Peoples are travel without purchasing tickets: Indian Railway has been facing extra loss of Rs. 5 core every single year on account of travelling without tickets. (3) Attack on Railways: The railways are attacked during the time of disturbances and violence that get up in any part of the country. Due to this the country is suffering a heavy loss of cores of rupees.

Merits of the Rail Transport

- It is relatively faster than road transport.
- It is suitable for carrying heavy goods in large quantities over long distances.
- Its operation is less affected be adverse weathers condition like rain, floods, fog, etc.

Demerits of the Rail Transport

- It is not available in remote parts of the country
- It provides services according to fixed time schedule and is not flexible for loading or unloading of goods at any place.
- It involves heavy losses of life as well as goods in case of accident.

5.2 Road Transportation:

The Road transport plays a pivot role in the country's transport system. In addition to this fact- that social and economic progress of the country depends on the development on the road, there is also a significant link of bringing about the emotional integration of the common accumulation. In fact, a road reaches the door steps. Only 20% of the national highway network (which carries 40% of traffic) is four-lane, and one- third of the rural population lacks access to an all-weather road. The roads are classified as: (1) National Highways. (2) State Highways. (3) District Roads. (4) Rural Roads, and (5) Special Purpose of military and ports etc. National highways are the best arterial route throughout the country and it caters the need of about 45% of total road transport demand. In 1950-51. Road network total length of roads was 4lakh km. out of it, 19.8 thousands km was national highway. The length of state highway was around 137.9 thousands km in 1998-99 against 56.8 thousand km in 1970-71. Recently the key innovation has been created of major new method of funding for national, state and rural roads. It has been named Central Road Fund (CRF). Moreover,

National Highway Development Project (NHDP) has been set up the expansion of the roads. According to “India Road and Transport Development Institute”. By extending the rural areas, it is possible to increase cultivable area by 25%. It encourages the sale of such perishable good as vegetable, fruits, milk, butter, etc. the roads are not built for specific vehicles. Different type of vehicles can be pressed in to service like, bullock cart, tanga, rickshaws, cycles, motors etc. along with that there are some problems also faced by Road Transport: (1) Heavy Taxes: There is heavy tax burden on motor transport in India. In India per vehicle tax burden is Rs.3500 while in America it is Rs.860 and In Britain Rs.470. (2) No Proper Maintenance: In India roads are not maintained properly compared to other country. Less than 0.1% of the national income spent on maintenance of the road while in Japan it is 3% of the national income. (3) Less Road in Rural Areas: Government should develop roads in rural areas. 60% of villages are facing the problem without roads in India. (4) Bad Condition of Roads: In India, roads are not maintained well and no timely repairs. It causes discomfort and quick decrease the value of vehicles.

Merits of Road Transport:

- Perishable goods can be transported at a faster speed by road carries over a short distance
- It is a flexible mode of transport as loading and unloading is possible at any destination. It provides door- to –door services.
- It helps people to travel and carry goods from one place to another, in place which are not connected by other means of transport like hilly areas.

Demerits of Road Transport:

- Due to limited carrying capacity road transport is not economical for long distance transportation of goods.
- Transportation of heavy goods or goods in bulk by road involves high cost.

5.3 Water Transport:

Water transport is the most easy and cheapest mode of traffic for both long and short distance transport. Oceans and rivers are the free gift of nature no cost is involved in construction. Before independence, there were many private shipping companies. But after independence, Eastern Shipping Corporation was established in 1950, in 1956 western shipping corporation was set up. In ancient period, shipping was one of the big industries in India. During 1860 to 1925, there were 102 Indian Shipping Industries but gradually all of them were damaged by the British. The history of Indian Shipping Companies from 1925 to 1945 is in – fact the history of Scandia Shipping company. It does not use the costlier resources as in the case of air or rail transport. In India Indians were much skilled in the building of ships and used to go to different distant countries like Persia, East Africa, Malaya and Eastern Island on their ships. In this context, Shri S.L.Haja has rightly stated that ‘Indian Naval Power was absolutely a great achievement of Indian Civilization. In 1947, the shipping Act was enacted. The licence was compulsory for to obtain the ship. In March, 1950- the Eastern Shipping Corporation was established with a capital of Rs.10cr. In 1956, the Western Shipping Corporation was established. In the year 1961 two corporation were merged with into Indian Shipping Corporation. There are three kinds of Water Transport: (1) Inland Water Transport. (2) Coastal Transport. (3) Oceanic Transport. The government has taken a lot of interest in the development of shipping sector by establishing a ship building industry in public sector, granting subsidy etc. Eighth plan intended to achieve the objective of attainment of a modern diversified fleet. And it may help in achieving the objective of export promotion and improve balance of payments. Current volume of India’s trade is completely large and it is likely to

further expand for sake of economic development of the country. The defence is more essential in shipping. And Foreign exchange is also utmost importance for country development. They will carry heavy and bulk goods at a low cost through water transport. And if compare to other transport the maintains cost also less. They also face some major problem in water transport they are: (1) Limited Area: The rivers and oceans are free gift of nature but the area of water transport is restricted. (2) Slow Speed: the failure of monsoon results into fall in the water – level of rivers making navigation difficult. (3) Less Safety: As against other means of transport, the safety is less water transport. During the sinking of boats and ships always emerge large.

Merits of Water Transport:

- It is a relatively economical mode of transport for bulky and heavy goods.
- It is a safe mode of transport with respect to occurrence of accidents.
- The cost of maintaining and constructing routes is very low most of them are naturally made.
- It promotes international trade.

Demerits of Water Transport:

- It is adversely affected by weather condition.
- Sea transport requires large on investment
- It is a slow moving mode of transport and therefore not suitable for transport of perishable goods.

5.4 Air Transport:

The air transport is the faster and the costlier mode of transport. In India there are several favourable circumstances for the development of air transport. The real progress was made during world war second. The credit goes to India for initiating the first Air service Asia in 1914 by post and Telegraph Department by carrying mail from Allahabad to Naini across the Ganga River. In the year of 1947, we had 27 airways companies in India and these have covered a distance of about 22cr km on their scheduled flight and carried about 3lakh passengers. And now they have covered a distance of about 10cr km and carry more than 72lakh passengers per year. The number of airport increased to 91 by 1990-91. And it includes 5 international airports at Mumbai, Kolkata, Chennai, Delhi ant Trivandrum. By the year 1972 in the public sector The International Airport Authority of India was established. The National Airport Authority on India was formed in 1986-June. In recently the Vayudoot and Pawan Hans are two airlines added to civil aviation. Previously the Air India International Services and India Airlines for domestic service were established in 1953. On the recommendation of this committee, in 1953 air transport was nationalized and three corporations were set up: (1) Air India International Corporation. (2) Indian Airline (3) Private Airline. It is named as high speed of transport. The passengers and goods can be transported speedily from one place to the other. Only the costly, light and perishable goods send through air transport. No need spend money for construction unlike railways and road transport. Only has to construct air-ports. And Air transport faced undernoted problems: (1) High Costs: the only air transport in India is becoming very costly day by day with rising operational cost. (2) Huge Investments: The Government is least capable of increasing the planes and airports in the country due to need of huge investment. (3) Inadequate Training Facilities: In airlines we are facing the problem of sufficient trained staff. There were no adequate facilities to train a large number of pilots in the country. (4) Maximization of Risks: Due to crime and terrorism, violence, take-over, etc. the risk is increasing day by day is more in air transport.

Merits of Air transport:

- It is very useful in transporting goods and passenger to the area, which are not accessible by any other means.
- It is the most convenient mode of transport during natural calamities.
- It provides vital support to the national security and defence.

Demerits of Air transport:

- It is relatively more expensive mode of transport.
- It is not suitable to transport in heavy and bulky goods.
- It is not suitable for short distance travel.
- In case of accident, it results in heavy losses of goods, property and life.

6. Benefits of Transportation:

Transportation plays a major role in the country. It can be realised from social as well economic of the nation. This can be generating by this sector in India during the plans. However, there are following points has been explained below:

6.1 Economic benefits:

- **Better Production in both Agriculture and Industrial Sector:** It has been helped to transport raw materials and labourers from and to the place of production and carrying the goods produced by these sectors of different parts of the country and other countries of the world. Also helps to increase the growth in industrial and agriculture sector.
- **Reduction in Cost of Production:** With increases in the price of fuel, the production allocated to transportation can be upward of 50%. It helps to reduce the cost of manufacturing goods and lower the price of the markets.
- **Reduction in Scarcity:** Many people believe that it helps to issues of scarcity can be solved by using more efficient production methods, like goods and factors in different regions of the country.
- **Growth in Foreign Trade:** The transportation system makes a network for among the different country. A countries exports and imports cannot a build without goods parts, shipping and cargo facilities. It also helps in promoting foreign trade of the country.
- **Promotion of Tourism:** Transportation sectors needs for tourism development and tourism promotions among others, to be maintained of the existing roads, construction of more roads, rail track, and sea and air transportation. It also helps promotes in tourism industry and several all other sectors.
- **Expands and Market:** Transportation helps to expands both on the domestic and international front with the expansion of the market both industry and agriculture of the transport network. For instance through the expansion of rail, water and road transport, it has got success making link between in different parts of the country and with other countries of the world.

6.2 Social Benefits:

- **More Employment Opportunities:** Transportation Industry more helps to create employment opportunities. It provides employment through helping mobility of worker. And about 1.54million people are working in Indian railway and in the same way people are employed in other transport sectors.
- **Education Expansion:** Education is one of the important parts in every other sector. Developing means of transport industry helps in the expansion of education even in

remote area of the country. It provides mobility of students, teachers. The transportation is the source of advertisement and in the same way they also help to expand the education.

- **Higher Standard of living:** A major objective of the government of a country is providing is good living to people. The standard of commodities increase our standard of living on which depends upon that good and services we consume. As a result, we enjoy the varieties of goods and services that produced in different corners of the world.
- **Relationship between Villages and Cities:** Now the villages can have employment opportunities available in the cities. So that they travel from village to city and vice versa and transportation has been reduce the distance between villages to city.

7. Challenges faced by transportation sector.

- ❖ **Driver shortage:** The transport industry facing a crisis of driver's shortages. While the new generation refuse to become a drivers.
- ❖ **Fuel cost:** The highest challenges transport industry is high fuel cost. If the fuel rates goes high is expected to increase transportation costs to the shippers.
- ❖ **Customer service:** Customers want the full clarity into where their delivery is at on time. Now days, the location of a shipment is as associated as your social network.
- ❖ **Government Regulations:** In addition to building and operating facilities, government regulates many aspects of freight transportation.
- ❖ **Environmental Issues:** The environmental impact of transport is significant because transport is major user of energy, and burns most of the world's petroleum. And it's creates Air pollution and the significant contribution to global warming through emission of carbon dioxide.
- ❖ **Economy:** The transport industry, one of the largest employers in the world, it provides service such as carrying passengers and freight.

8. Carrier Opportunities in Transport Industry:

The transportation industry has created large number of employment opportunities for people. And also this will help for our country to decrease the unemployment. About more than 1.54 million people are working in railway. Same way Lakhs of people are employed in roadway, shipping and air transport. Following some carrier opportunities are mentioned below:

- **Road Transportation Manager:** Road transportation managers take overall responsibility for managing the exaction, direction, and coordination for all transportation matters with in the organisation. These includes organising the schedule and route, ensuring the efficient and safe, running of vehicles carrying passengers and goods by roads and make sure that drivers are aware of the roads.
- **Road Transportation Clerks:** They are responsible for carrying out tasks under the direction of transportation manager. Their tasks are mainly administrative and financial duties. The goods and passengers by road move from one place to another place and are likely to involve the use of computer systems. Their duties may include handling accounts, organising vehicles and deliveries, customer enquiries and arranging staffs roads.
- **Engine engineers:** A person who operates a train, usually called an engineer or train driver outside North America. He operates large trains carrying the goods and

passengers between the stations. And if any necessary minor adjustment and any documentation issue with regards to the goods or passengers.

- **Railroad Conductors:** They will work on trains carrying freight or people, train conductors may either assist with cargo or those passengers' needs and safety are addressed. They will work according to the schedule and work team to ensure that train runs on same. And make any necessary announcements along the way.
- **The commercial division:** The commercial divides all commercial responsibilities like ticket checking at ticket checking station; catering and vending stall etc. and write about the responsibility of Administrative and management of stations, reservation and announcements on the platforms etc.
- **Railway engineers:** The Railway engineers are engaged in the technical and construction activities for making, sure the plan for right track, like, dealing with the design, construction and operation of all types of railway systems.
- **Customs Department officers:** Custom officers are the persons working on behalf of government who keep an eye on incoming goods in to the country such as gold, electronics, etc. which has duty to be paid when importing from other countries. Custom duty is charged for those items when goods are imported from other countries since it has major impact on our economy, hence duty will be charged for imported items.
- **Immigration Department:** A visa is form of permission for a non- citizen to travel, transit or remain in a particular country. Immigration department is responsible for checking the correct entry of individuals arriving at seaports and airports. The officers also inspect documentation, where essential and remove illegal entrants.
- **Aviation Department:** Aviation sector is generating job in various filed such as Air cargo, airport ground staff, cabin crew, pilots, Aeronautical Engineers, Airline ticketing etc. Aviation sector also plays an integral role in developing countries economy. Air transport is faster than any other transportation and also time savings. Some commodities are time sensitive such as human remaining, perishable items, life and death medical consignment etc. and for this type of consignment air transport is ideal, other than this air transport will help in industrial sector as well to have faster production.
- **Merchant Navy Department:** In earlier days women were not generally allowed to take up jobs in merchant navy but in the past few years have seen lot of changes with in women taking up jobs as ship doctor and radio officers. It deals transporting the cargo and occasionally, passengers, by sea. The main opportunities in the merchant navy are navigating officers, radio officers and marine engineers.

9. Comparison for the best mode of Transportation:

In the below table we compared four modes of transportation on its speed, dependability, frequency, availability, flexibility, and cost. Road transportation is the best among the four modes of transportation as this gives greater connectivity and door to door step service in the form of employment opportunities, education, and business. The cost is also cheaper when compared to other mode of transportation along with that they can carry heavy goods also. The rural area people too get more benefited by this transport. Agriculture and industrial sectors which are placed far from city limits get connectivity of road transport.

Table: 1 Comparison for the best mode of Transportation

Mode	Speed	Dependability In meeting Schedule	Frequency of Shipment	Availability in Different Location	Flexibility in Handling	Cost
Rail	Average	Average	Low	Low	High	Average
Water	Very Slow	Average	Very Low	Limited	Very High	Very Low
Truck	Fast	High	High	Very Extensive	Average	High
Air	Very Fast	High	Average	Average	Low	Very High

10. Share of different mode of transport in India’s GDP

Fig: 2 share of different mode of transportation

Source: Central Statistical Organisation

The above graph says The Gross domestic product (GDP) is a measure of the income of a country. It measures the final value of goods and services produced in an economy or in a particular area/industry/sector. The percentage is share of entire transportation sector in Gross Domestic product in 20011-12 was 4.13% and in 2016-17 was 4.11% decreased by 0.2%. Currently transport sector accounts for a share of 6.3% in Indian’s GDP. Road transportation has emerged as the dominant segment in India’s transportation sector with a share of 5.4% in India’s GDP.

12. Conclusion:

Transportation industry has a crucial role to play in economic development. It has been accepted that the provision of a high quality transport system is a necessary in the aids of national development. It is necessary to elevation the development of the various transport modes in an shared manner that will lead to the understanding of an efficient, sustainable, safe and regionally balanced transportation system, where each mode of transport operates in its field of economy and usefulness, with competitive and non-discriminatory prices that are adequate to support progressive development of transport infrastructure and services. This would also enable the comparative advantages and economic efficiencies to be properly reflected in the users costs.

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